

Determination of 2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyldibenzoyl-methane in Non-aqueous Medium by Enthalpimetric, Conductometric and Potentiometric Methods

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In continuation of our earlier work on the titrimetric determination of 2-hydroxy-5-methyldibenzoyl-methane¹ in non-aqueous medium, the present work was undertaken to determine 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyldibenzoylmethane (HBMDDBM) in non-aqueous medium by enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric methods.

Effect of dilution : Effect of dilution was studied by choosing a suitable amount (6.64 mg) of HBMDDBM and enthalpimetric titrations were performed using different volumes of acetone under identical conditions (Table 2). From the results it seems that the volume of solvent dose not have any noticeable effect.

TABLE 1—TITRATION OF HBMDDBM, EFFECT OF NATURE OF TITRANT

Titrant	Enthalpimetric			Conductometric			Potentiometric		
	Wt. taken	Wt. found	% Error	Wt. taken	Wt. found	%Error	Wt. taken	Wt. found	%Error
	mg	mg		mg	mg		mg	mg	
n-Bu ₄ NOH	4.00	3.928	-1.8	3.948	3.845	-2.6	4.051	4.002	-1.2
Alcoholic KOH	4.00	3.968	-0.8	3.948	3.896	-1.3	4.051	4.034	-0.4

Results and Discussion

The end-points are indicated by sudden break in the curve accompanied by sharp rise in temperature. Titration curve for conductometric titration did not show sharp break, but the end-points could be determined by extrapolation. However errors in estimation were comparatively large. Potentiometric titration curves showed sharp rise in potential at the end-point. The end-points were determined by differential method to get accurate results. Comparison of the results obtained by three different methods for n-Bu₄NOH and alcoholic KOH (Table 1) shows that alcoholic KOH is the most suitable titrant for the estimation of HBMDDBM. Hence alcoholic KOH was used as a titrant for further experiments.

Effect of concentration of the solute : Stock solution (containing 3.32 mg of HBMDDBM per ml) was prepared and different volumes of this

TABLE 2—ENTHALPIMETRIC TITRATION OF HBMDDBM, EFFECT OF DILUTION

Solvent : acetone, Titrant : alcoholic KOH

Sl. no.	Vol. of solution taken ml	Vol. of acetone added ml	Wt. of HBMDDBM titrated mg	Wt. found mg	%Error
1.	2.0	0.0	6.64	6.699	+0.9
2.	2.0	1.0	6.64	6.580	-0.9
3.	2.0	2.0	6.64	6.586	-0.8
4.	2.0	3.0	6.64	6.679	+0.6
5.	2.0	4.0	6.64	6.673	+0.5
6.	2.0	5.0	6.64	6.580	-0.9
7.	2.0	6.0	6.64	6.593	-0.7
8.	2.0	7.0	6.64	6.581	-0.9

TABLE 3—TITRATIONS OF HBMDDBM IN ACETONE WITH ALCOHOLIC KOH AND n-Bu₄NOH, EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

Sl. no.	Weight titrated mg	Enthalpimetric		Conductometric		Potentiometric	
		Weight mg	% Error	Weight mg	% Error	Weight mg	% Error
With alcoholic KOH							
1.	0.83	0.820	-1.2	0.820	-1.1	0.821	-1.0
2.	1.66	1.639	-1.4	1.640	-1.2	1.641	-1.1
3.	3.32	3.300	-0.6	3.283	-1.1	3.293	-0.8
4.	6.64	6.593	-0.7	6.566	-1.1	6.586	-0.8
5.	9.96	9.930	-0.3	9.900	-0.6	9.930	-0.3
6.	13.28	13.253	-0.2	13.187	-0.7	13.266	-0.1
7.	16.60	16.351	-1.5	16.450	-0.9	16.583	-0.1
8.	19.92	19.621	-1.5	19.740	-0.9	19.880	-0.2
9.	23.24	22.728	-2.2	22.868	-1.6	23.170	-0.3
10.	26.56	25.975	-2.2	26.028	-2.0	26.763	+0.3
11.	29.88	29.103	-2.6	29.252	-2.1	29.640	-0.8
12.	33.20	32.170	-3.1	32.436	-2.3	32.834	-1.1
With n- Bu ₄ NOH :							
1.	0.83	0.819	-1.3	0.820	-1.2	0.821	-1.0
2.	1.66	1.630	-1.8	1.636	-1.4	1.641	-1.1
3.	3.32	3.293	-0.8	3.280	-1.2	3.283	-1.1
4.	6.64	6.593	-0.7	6.573	-1.0	6.586	-0.8
5.	9.96	9.920	-0.4	9.900	-0.6	9.930	-0.3
6.	13.28	13.187	-0.7	13.160	-0.9	13.253	-0.2
7.	16.60	16.284	-1.9	16.467	-0.8	16.583	-0.1
8.	19.92	19.521	-2.0	19.621	-1.5	19.860	-0.3
9.	23.24	22.728	-2.2	22.821	-1.8	23.170	-0.3
10.	26.56	25.922	-2.4	26.692	+0.5	26.427	-0.5
11.	29.88	29.043	-2.8	30.507	+2.1	29.611	-0.9
12.	33.20	32.038	-3.5	33.930	+2.2	32.602	-1.8

solution (0.5–20.0 ml) were diluted to 20 ml to get the solutions of different concentrations. 2 ml of each of these solutions were separately titrated enthalpimetrically, conductometrically and potentiometrically with n-Bu₄NOH and alcoholic KOH and the results (Table 3) were compared. It is observed that HBMDDBM can be quantitatively estimated in the range 0.8–14.0 mg by enthalpimetric titration. Beyond this limit the percentage error becomes appreciable. Conductometric titration also gave good results in the range 0.8–20.0 mg of HBMDDBM, but the percentage error was relatively small. Potentiometric titration was found to yield best result amongst the three methods. Error in estimation was found to be minimum (usually less than $\pm 1.1\%$) and the method can estimate 0.8–33.0 mg of HBMDDBM accurately under the experimental conditions. However, enthalpimetric method surpasses the potentiometric method in

simplicity and fastness and hence is recommended for quick estimation of HBMDDBM.

Standard and mean deviations : Standard and mean deviations for titrations of HBMDDBM with alcoholic KOH were found to be 0.37 and 0.21 for enthalpimetric titration, 0.38 and 0.17 for conductometric titration, and 0.34 and 0.12 for potentiometric titration.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade, and wherever necessary purified further employing standard methods. HBMDDBM was synthesised by the known method² and its purity was tested by its m.p. (92°) and molecular weight (332). All solvents were made anhydrous by known methods³. Tetra-n-butylammonium hydroxide (n-

NOTE

Bu₄NOH) and KOH in isopropanol (alcoholic KOH) were prepared, standardised and preserved as reported earlier¹.

A Systronics 304 conductometer was used for conductometric titration. The potential measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ with a Systronics 335 pH meter. Glass electrode as reference and antimony/antimony oxide electrode were used as indicator electrode.

Procedure : All titration were performed in nitrogen atmosphere in triplicate in acetone medium. Methods for enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations were necessarily the same

as reported earlier¹. End-points were determined graphically.

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References

1. G. D. TEMBHARE, M. M. CHINCHOLKAR and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 669.
2. H. S. MAHAL and K. VENKATRAMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1767.
3. J. KUCHARSKY and L. SAFARIK, "Titration in Non-aqueous Solvent", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, New York, 1974, p. 49.

